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Closing the gap: promoting suspect communities’ cooperation with airport security

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Abstract

In the aftermaths of 9/11, aviation security is a central component of counterterrorism. To mitigate threats whilst maintaining flight schedules, airport security officers require the cooperation of all passengers, but especially of ethnic minorities perceived as posing a potential threat to homeland security, often referred to as “suspect communities”. Passengers from suspect communities are subject to rigorous screening, but are also regarded as a source of information, making their cooperation even more important than that of other passengers. Nevertheless, suspect communities’ cooperation with airport security, and the gap between their attitudes and those of other passengers, were not yet examined. The current study utilizes a survey of 1970 passengers at the Ben-Gurion airport in Israel, examining passengers’ perceptions of airport security and their willingness to cooperate. We find that passengers belonging to the suspect community of Israeli Muslims were less willing to cooperate with security procedures than all other passengers. However, when controlling for passengers’ perceptions of legitimacy and procedural justice, Israeli Muslims were more willing to cooperate with airport security than Israeli Jews. The findings highlight the importance of legitimacy and procedural justice perceptions in obtaining the cooperation of suspect communities, and suggest practical pathways for improving cooperation.

Introduction

In the unstable reality of ever-evolving terrorist threats, the importance of aviation security remains undisputed. As demonstrated in the downing of an aircraft in Egypt in 2015, the attempt to down an airliner in Somalia in 2016, the 2016 armed attacks against airports in Brussels and Istanbul¹, and ISIS threat in 2016 to use "...a device placed in either Heathrow, LAX or JFK airports,"² effective counterterrorism through airport security screening remains a central concern.

Similar to other counterterrorism tasks, airport security officers rely heavily on passengers' obedience and cooperation. To achieve effective screening procedures and mitigate potential threats, while allowing for commercial airports to function, security officers need passengers to follow instructions, be transparent and clear when questioned, and voluntarily alert officers or provide information³. Of special importance is the cooperation of ethnic minorities that, due to their possible relations with hostile groups or countries, are perceived as posing a potential threat to homeland security, often referred to as "suspect communities."⁴ The significance of suspect communities' cooperation in counterterrorism is twofold: first, the perceived threat they pose leads to rigorous screening procedures, often resulting in passengers' negative feelings⁵. In turn, these negative feelings may induce clashes between passengers and security officers, hampering the screening procedure as well as authorities' long-term relations with the community⁶. To avoid these clashes, airport security officers require passengers to cooperate despite how they may feel about the uncomfortable procedures. Second, while suspect community passengers may pose a risk, they are also the best source of information about potential threats⁷. Having close ties to their community means that they are able to identify risks, and cooperate with security officers to mitigate

them. Hence, while the cooperation of suspect communities with airport security may be difficult to achieve, it is key for effective counterterrorism.

Studies examining suspect communities' cooperation with counterterrorism in their neighbourhoods found that cooperation is largely affected by perceptions of the quality of police treatment⁸. However, in the time-sensitive high-risk process of security screening at airports, suspect communities are often subject to profiling, additional procedures and scrutiny, hampering their evaluations of airport security⁹. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that passengers from suspect communities will be less willing to cooperate with airport security than other passengers, and that this attitude will be largely affected by their perceptions of airport security. Nevertheless, to date, suspect communities' willingness to cooperate with airport security, the effect of their perceptions of airport security on their cooperation, and the difference in cooperation between them and other passengers, have not been examined.

The current study addresses the willingness of suspect communities to cooperate with airport security, and the difference between their attitudes to those of other passengers. We do so by utilizing an attitudes survey conducted among 1970 Israeli Muslims, Israeli Jews and foreign passengers flying from Ben-Gurion international airport in 2013-2014. First, we review the literature on suspect communities, and recent evidence on their willingness to cooperate with counterterrorism in their own neighbourhoods. We then describe counterterrorism in the airport context, the way screening procedures may shape passengers' perceptions, and the potential effect of these perceptions of on cooperation. We discuss Muslim citizens in Israel¹⁰ as a suspect community, and describe our research hypothesis, data collection and analysis. Using a series of OLS models, we find that in line with the literature, Muslim passengers were the least willing to cooperate with airport security officers, less than all other passengers. However, when considering passengers' perceptions

of airport screening's legitimacy and procedural justice, Israeli Muslims were more willing to cooperate with airport security than the majority group of Israeli Jews. We propose that the message of inclusion implanted in fair procedures can undermine the effect of ethnic identity and encourage cooperation among suspect community members.

Suspect communities and counterterrorism

First proposed by Hillyard in 1993¹¹, the term “suspect communities” was originally used to describe how members of the Irish community were often suspected for involvement in terrorism just for being Irish. In the words of Hillyard, “...they are not believed to be involved in or guilty of some illegal act... people are suspect primarily because they are Irish” (p. 7). This definition of suspect communities refers to the treatment received from the police or the justice system by members of a specific community, not because of any personal suspicion of involvement in unlawful behaviour, but rather because they are linked – by markers such as physical appearance, accent or last name – to a community suspected to be involved in terrorism¹².

The application of this term to Muslim communities after 9/11, while intuitive, is subject to some deliberation in the literature¹³. The declared “war on terrorism” has described Islamic extremism as the common enemy, implying that Muslim residents of Western democracies are to be cautiously regarded as “the enemy within”¹⁴. Indeed, recent findings suggest that Muslims in Europe and the US are often treated by authorities as members of a suspect community: subject to more stop and search procedures in every day policing, and to profiling and scrutiny in airports and borders¹⁵. In turn, this discriminating treatment may

foster feelings of being targeted and profiled, potentially hampering Muslim's relations with authorities and undermining their willingness to cooperate¹⁶.

At the same time, the increasing demand for effective counterterrorism has stressed the importance of suspect communities working hand in hand with the police. Specifically, scholars and practitioners have highlighted the normative, as well as practical, advantages of fruitful cooperation between the Muslim diaspora and the police in counterterrorism¹⁷. As stated by Scotland Yard's anti-terror chief, Commander Richard Walton, "we depend on the cooperation of communities... we cannot be everywhere, we depend on people trusting us and coming forward to tell us of their concerns"¹⁸. Hence, legal authorities are aiming to gain the trust and cooperation of the same communities targeted and suspected for the potential threat they pose.

Promoting suspect communities' cooperation

How can suspect communities be encouraged to cooperate with counterterrorism, despite the negative feelings often induced by the discriminating treatment they receive? A large body of empirical studies support the importance of citizen's attitudes towards the police, and specifically perceptions of police legitimacy, procedural justice and effectiveness as predictors of cooperation¹⁹. A normative value in democratic societies, citizen's perceptions of police legitimacy were found to be the primary predictor of cooperation, as well as encourage more general law obedient behaviour²⁰. One's perceptions of the fairness of policing procedures, also known as procedural justice, also affect their willingness to cooperate²¹. Perceptions of procedural justice are not based on the outcome of this process, but on public perceptions of four procedural components: (1) a sense of *participation* in the process; (2) a sense of *respectful treatment* on behalf of the police; (3) perceptions of

neutrality and impartial decision making; and (4) the belief that the police have *trustworthy motives*²². The outcome of the procedure – police effectiveness – has also been found to predict cooperation²³. Evaluations of police effectiveness are subjective evaluations of the policing outcome, such as preventing crime or maintaining public order²⁴.

Recent findings suggest that perceptions of legitimacy, procedural justice and effectiveness may also predict suspect communities' cooperation with counterterrorism in their own neighbourhoods²⁵. Huq et al.²⁶ examined the willingness of Muslim residents in the UK to cooperate with the police on counterterrorism. Using a phone survey of 300 participants, they found that perceptions of procedural justice and police legitimacy were the most important predictors of cooperation. In the US, Tyler et al.²⁷ examined cooperation using interviews with 300 Muslims residents. Here again, they found that procedural justice was the primary predictor of cooperation. Similar results were found for Muslims in Australia²⁸. In a recent study on Muslims' cooperation with counterterrorism, Cherney and Murphy²⁹ note that promoting Australian Muslim's cooperation is particularly challenging, as the declared "war on terrorism has left many of them feeling targeted and stigmatized." Accordingly, they found that feeling targeted hampered Muslims' trust in the police, perceptions of just procedures, and their willingness to cooperate with counterterrorism.

The studies reviewed above suggest that suspect communities' cooperation with the authorities bears special importance, both as a source of information for counterterrorism and as a mean to preserve their relations with the police and avoid violence. At the same time, when members of suspect communities feel targeted, profiled and discriminated based on their ethnicity, they may perceive authorities and procedures as negative, hampering their willingness to cooperate. In this regard, the context of airport security represents a unique and stressful policing arena, manifestly employing targeted and discriminating measures for

suspect communities. However, to date, suspect communities' willingness to cooperate with airport security has not yet been examined. Beyond the normative importance of airport authorities in democratic societies maintaining good relations with all passengers, and the practical necessity of suspect communities' cooperation to mitigate terrorism, the cooperation of suspect communities with airport procedures carries financial implications: "Problematic" passengers who choose to negotiate during the screening process result in direct costs to manpower and delays in schedule³⁰. The next section will review the unique circumstances of airport security procedures, their potential effect on passengers' cooperation, and specifically on the cooperation of passengers from suspect communities.

Suspect communities' cooperation with airport security

In light of the growing number of passengers going through international airports, and the constant threats of aviation terrorism, increasing resources are invested in an effort to improve airport security while maintaining passengers' satisfaction³¹. However, for some of the passengers, aviation security often dictates discriminating treatment³². Ethnic profiling of suspect communities is rarely officially declared, but is common practice in many airports. In the US, passengers from 13 Muslim states are subject to enhanced screening procedures³³; Some level of profiling, based on markers such as nationality, ethnic origin or religion, also exist in other countries, including Canada and Europe³⁴.

In Israel, while racial profiling is not an official screening method, Muslims are subject to more rigorous procedures than other passengers, including being separated from fellow passengers, long questioning by several officers, and manual search of their suitcases and body³⁵. As suggested by (Blinded), Israeli Muslims are perceived as a potential threat to aviation security due to their self-identification as Palestinians on the one hand, and their

ethnonational affiliation with hostile Arab countries on the other hand³⁶. A report published by the Arab Association for Human Rights (HRA) suggests that while profiling is not a declared policy, Israeli Muslim passengers are often subject to what they perceived to be discriminating, humiliating and rude screening procedures³⁷.

Ethnic profiling and discrimination often leave passengers from suspect communities feeling offended and humiliated, alienating them from authorities³⁸. In this regard, airport screening procedures can be perceived as a form of high-policing, accordingly provoking feelings of hostile treatment and lower perceptions of legitimacy³⁹. Indeed, studies from North America, Europe and Israel have found evidence for discriminating treatment and the feelings it provokes. Passengers from suspect communities were subject to more profiling and severe security screening procedures⁴⁰. Accordingly, they perceived airport security procedures to be less justified, less legitimate, and more threatening to their personal dignity than other passengers⁴¹. In Israel, Muslim passengers felt that security procedures caused embarrassment and ill feelings, leading to lower trust in airport security officers, and to less overall satisfaction with airport security checks⁴². In the UK, Blackwood et al.⁴³ interviewed 38 Scottish Muslims on their encounters with airport authorities. They found that their interviewees shared a similar “Muslim airport story” of being targeted and profiled, and interpreted it as lack of respect for them as British, as Muslims and as respectable members of society. However, even under the scrutiny dictated by aviation security, perceptions of procedural justice remain important: Langley examined the effect of a procedurally just treatment on passengers that were subject to Schedule 7 of the Terrorism Act 2000 while flying through an international airport in the UK. He found that a procedurally just protocol supported positive evaluations of airport security legitimacy, as well as passenger’s willingness to cooperate with security officers⁴⁴.

The above findings suggest that passengers from suspect communities often perceive airport security procedures to be humiliating and discriminating. Accordingly, they perceive airport security to be less legitimate and procedurally just than other passengers. Based on the correlation between these perceptions and cooperation in other contexts of policing, we expect that passengers from suspect communities will be less willing to cooperate with airport security than other passengers. In-line with the literature on perceptions of legitimacy and just treatment as predictors of cooperation, we also expect suspect communities' willingness to cooperate to be mediated by their perceptions of airport security. However, these studies did not examine the willingness of passengers from suspect communities to cooperate with airport security procedures, the effect of their perceptions of airport security on their cooperation, or the gap between their cooperation to that of other passengers.

The current study examines the willingness of Israeli Muslim, Israeli Jewish and foreign passengers to cooperate with airport security, while controlling for their perceptions of legitimacy, procedural justice and effectiveness of the screening procedures. We do so by analysing a survey of 1970 passengers, traveling through Ben-Gurion international airport in Israel. In the next section, we detail the research hypotheses, explain our choice to focus on Israeli Muslims as a case study, and present the study methodology and findings.

Research Hypotheses

Based on the studies on suspect communities' perceptions of airport security procedures, and the effect of these perceptions on cooperation found in other policing contexts, we expect passengers from the suspect community of Israeli Muslims to be less willing to cooperate with airport security than other passengers, and for this attitude to be mediated by their perceptions of the security procedures. Specifically, we make the following hypotheses:

1. Muslim passengers will be less willing to cooperate with airport security than all other passengers.
2. When controlling for the known predictors of cooperation – perceptions of legitimacy, procedural justice and effectiveness, the “cooperation gap” between Muslims and other passengers will be abridged.

Case study: Israeli Muslim passengers at the Ben-Gurion airport

In the Israeli deeply-divided society, Muslim citizens are the largest ethnic minority group, representing over 17% of Israeli population⁴⁵. Similar to other ethnic minorities worldwide, Israeli Muslims are native-born, full citizens of Israel, but are also extremely marginalized and disadvantaged in comparison to the majority group of Israeli Jews⁴⁶. In regards to their relations with the authorities, Israeli Muslims suffer from none to underrepresentation in the police and other law enforcement agencies; biased policing behaviour; and a chronic tradition of mistrust and alienation⁴⁷. Accordingly, Blinded⁴⁸ found that in line with the literature on other ethnic minorities, Israeli Arabs (84% of them Muslims) view the police more negatively than Israeli Jews in almost every dimension. An important consideration in the definition of Israeli Muslims as a suspect community is their perception of being targeted by the police as a potential security threat; Similar to other Muslim minority groups in the post 9/11 western reality of policing, Israeli Muslims often perceive themselves as targeted and profiled⁴⁹.

Israeli Muslims’ charged relations with law enforcement authorities, and their profiling as posing potential threat, are of special importance in the context of aviation security⁵⁰. In the Ben-Gurion international airport in Israel, security officers employ a long list of security procedures, such as gathering intelligence on passengers, regular searches inside and outside

aircrafts, and CCTV⁵¹. However, from the point of view of the passengers arriving to the airport, the security screening process mainly concerns the procedures they go through from the moment they check-in until the flight leaves⁵². For most passengers, this process only includes standard questioning, metal detectors and X-ray machines; but when physical or other markers suggest that the passenger belongs to a suspect community, he or she may go through advanced questioning, physical search and even separate interrogation⁵³.

The study

To examine suspect communities' willingness to cooperate with airport security, we conducted a survey among 1970 passengers leaving Israel through Ben-Gurion international airport in July-August, 2013 and October, 2014. Ben-Gurion airport is the main point of entrance to Israel, with more than 14 million passengers passing through in 2014⁵⁴. All security procedures at the airport are conducted by The Israeli Airports Authority (IAA), responsible for the safety of passengers and the prevention of terror attacks in seven airports in Israel. To collect data, we randomly approached passengers after they completed the security screening process, and were waiting in the duty free zone to board their flight. We analyse the results using a step-wise OLS regression model, to examine whether (1) Israeli Muslim passengers are less willing to cooperate with airport security officers than other passengers; and (2) whether this gap persists once the predictors of cooperation – legitimacy, procedural justice and effectiveness – are controlled for.

The sample and data collection

The survey was conducted in two separate waves of data collection, during July and August 2013 and October 2014. For each wave, research assistants waited for the passengers to complete the screening process at the duty-free zone of the main airport terminal, and

approached each passenger they came across. After a short explanation regarding the purpose of the study and the questionnaire, the research assistants suggested to the passengers to take part in the survey. To encourage passengers' participation, passengers who completed the survey were offered free coffee and pastry in one of the terminal coffee shops.

Passengers completed the survey in one of four languages – English (mainly used by foreign passengers); Hebrew (mainly used by Israeli Jews); Arabic (mainly used by Israeli Muslims); and Russian (mainly used by Israeli Jews who immigrated to Israel from Russia). The choice of languages was made available to help passengers feel convenient and better understand the questions. Whenever necessary, a research assistant assisted the participants to understand and complete the questionnaire. The final sample included 1970 passengers from three groups: Israeli Jews (660), Israeli Muslims (687), and foreign passengers (623)⁵⁵. We estimated a response rate of about 40%, similar to previous airport studies⁵⁶.

The survey and main variables

The survey included 26 statements, measuring the dependent variable – passenger's willingness to cooperate with airport security, as well as the predictors of cooperation: perceptions of airport security's legitimacy, procedural justice, and effectiveness. The participants completed the survey stating their level of agreement with each statement, from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The statements were based both on similar surveys measuring perceptions of police legitimacy and willingness to cooperate with the police, with an adaptation to the world of aviation security, and on previous surveys conducted at the BenGurion airport in Israel⁵⁷. The survey also included questions relating to socio-demographic characteristics – such as passengers' ethnicity, age, gender, levels of education and income, and their flight characteristics – their flying companions, the reason for the

flight, and the number of flights taken in the passing year (See appendix 1 and 2 for the descriptive statistics of control variables).

In line with the recommendations in the literature (e.g. Reisig et al.⁵⁸), the construction of scales was guided by factor analysis (an examination of the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin measure of sampling adequacy suggested that the sample was appropriate for factor analysis; KMO = 0.94). See Table 1 for the factor analysis and complete list of the items used to construct each scale.

Table 1 about here

The dependent variable, willingness to cooperate, was constructed by averaging passengers' level of agreement with three statements (Cronbach's $\alpha=.66$; $N=1940$; Range=15; $M=4.32$; $SD=.73$), such as "I will not hesitate to give information to security officers" and "If I have suspicions regarding a person or an object, I will immediately contact a security officer." The first independent variable, perceptions of legitimacy, was constructed by averaging passengers' level of agreement with four statements (Cronbach's $\alpha=.82$; $N=1962$; Range=1-5; $M=4.21$; $SD=.84$), such as "I have trust in the airport security at Ben-Gurion airport" and "I feel appreciation and respect towards the airport security officers." The second independent variable, perceptions of procedural justice, was constructed by averaging passengers' level of agreement with six statements (Cronbach's $\alpha=.81$; $N=1797$; Range=1-5; $M=4.07$; $SD=.61$), such as "The security officers at Ben-Gurion airport gave me the feeling that they care about me" and "The airport security officers at Ben-Gurion airport treated me with politeness and dignity." The third independent variable, the perceived effectiveness of airport security, was constructed by averaging passengers' level of agreement with two statements (Cronbach's $\alpha=.61$; $N=1942$; Range=1-5; $M=4.11$; $SD=.91$): "The security procedures at Ben-Gurion airport contributed to my sense of security on the flight" and "The

security division at Ben-Gurion airport is efficient in handling security threats.”

Findings

Passengers' willingness to cooperate with airport security

The current study was designed to assess the differences between passengers from suspect communities and other passengers in their willingness to cooperate with airport security. We examined whether a difference between these groups exists, and if so, if it remains significant once the predictors of cooperation described in the literature – perceptions of legitimacy, procedural justice and effectiveness, are controlled for.

To answer these questions, we first compare the answers of Israeli Jewish passengers, Israeli Muslim passengers and foreign passengers to the three statements constructing the dependent variable in our survey. The results are presented in table 2.

Table 2 about here

As can be seen in table 2, passengers from all groups generally expressed high levels of willingness to cooperate with airport security ($M=4.15-4.61$, on a scale of 1-5). However, there are significant differences between the groups in two out of three statements, describing passenger's willingness to assist a security officer and to contact a security officer if they have suspicions regarding a person or an object at the airport. For these two statements, passengers from the majority group of Israeli Jews were most willing to cooperate with security officers, followed by foreign passengers. As expected, passengers from the suspect community of Israeli Muslims were the least willing to cooperate with airport security.

To further explore the differences in cooperation between the groups, we compared the mean differences in passenger's willingness to cooperate. The results are presented in table 3.

Table 3 about here

As can be seen in table 3, there were significant differences in the overall willingness to cooperate between Muslim and non-Muslim passengers. Israeli Jewish passengers were most willing to cooperate with airport security, followed by foreign passengers. Muslim passengers were the least willing to cooperate with airport security⁵⁹.

Predictors of passenger's cooperation

As reviewed above, the first part of the analysis suggested a significant gap between Israeli Muslim passengers and all other passengers in cooperation. The second part of the analysis explores the stability of this gap: when the predictors of cooperation are taken into account, would Muslim passengers still be the least willing to cooperate?

In table 4 we present a series of OLS regression models. In model I we test whether passenger's ethnic identity ("Israeli Muslims" and "foreigners" vs. "Israeli Jews") affects their willingness to cooperate with airport security. In model II we add passenger's sociodemographic characteristics, as well as factors related to their flight. In model III, IV and V we add passengers' perceptions of the effectiveness of security procedures (model III), airport security legitimacy (Model IV) and procedural justice (Model V), and examine whether the effect of ethnicity on cooperation remains significant. The model is statistically significant ($p < .001$), and explains 38% of the variance in passengers' willingness to cooperate with airport security. Tolerance levels for all variables were larger than .38, suggesting no multicollinearity problems⁶⁰.

Table 4 about here

As can be seen in table 4, model I indicates that passenger's ethnicity has a significant effect on their willingness to cooperate: belonging to the suspect community of Israeli Muslims has a strong negative effect on cooperation. Being a foreign passenger also undermines cooperation, although the effect is less important. Adding personal and flight-related characteristics in model II, we find that age has a positive effect on cooperation, so that older passengers were more willing to cooperate with airport security than younger passengers. Interestingly, controlling for personal characteristics eliminates the negative effect the social identity of foreign passengers has on cooperation. In other words, when the age of the passenger and other personal characteristics are taken into account, foreign passengers are as willing to cooperate with airport security as passengers from the majority group of Israeli Jews. For Israeli Muslim passengers, however, even when socio-demographic characteristics are accounted for, the effect of ethnicity on cooperation remains negative and significant.

In model III, passengers' perceptions of the effectiveness of airport security procedures are added. While perceptions of effectiveness have a significant and strong positive effect on cooperation, the negative effect of ethnic identity remains: passengers from the suspect community of Israeli Muslims were less willing to cooperate with airport security, even after their perceptions of airport security's effectiveness were accounted for. In model IV, passenger's perceptions of airport security's legitimacy are added, with a strong and positive effect on cooperation. When considering the effect of legitimacy, the effect of being part of a suspect community on cooperation changes from negative to positive; however, this effect is not significant. Finally, in model V we add the primary predictor of cooperation – passengers' perceptions of airport security's procedural justice. Results indicate that when Israeli Muslim passengers hold positive perceptions of airport security, the effect of ethnicity on cooperation not only changes from negative to positive, but becomes significant. In other words,

controlling for passenger's perceptions of the screening procedures not only undermined the gap between Israeli Muslims and other passengers in cooperation, but meant that Israeli Muslim passengers were more willing to cooperate with airport security officers than any other passenger.

Discussion

The current study examines the willingness of suspect communities to cooperate with airports security. Specifically, we tested whether Muslim passengers were less willing to cooperate with airport security than other passengers, and whether considering passenger's perceptions of legitimacy, procedural justice and effectiveness can help decrease this gap. We found that ethnicity has a significant effect on passengers' willingness to cooperate with airport security: passengers from the majority group of Israeli Jews were most willing to cooperate, whilst Israeli Muslim passengers were least willing to cooperate. Importantly, the gap between suspect community passengers and majority group passengers remained significant when controlling not only for personal and flight related characteristics, but also for the perceived effectiveness of security procedures. This finding is in line with previous studies from other policing contexts, emphasising the similarity between aviation security and other counterterrorism arenas⁶¹. The significantly lower willingness of Israeli Muslims to cooperate with airport security is not surprising, considering the severe security screening they endure, and their lower general evaluations of airport security⁶². In this regard, the gap also corresponds to the negative perceptions of airport security found among non-white minority passengers in the US⁶³.

However, the central finding in the present study is that this gap between suspect community passengers and other passengers, however understandable, is not inevitable. When considering passenger's perceptions of airport security's legitimacy and procedural justice, the negative effect of belonging to a suspect community not only disappears, but is overturned. In other words, when Israeli Muslim passengers perceived the screening process as legitimate and procedurally just, they were *more* willing to cooperate with airport security than any other passengers. To our knowledge, this is the first time that the gap in cooperation between suspect communities and the majority group is examined. The findings suggest that while a gap in attitudes exists, it can be breached through wider perceptions of the authority and related procedures.

How can this change in attitudes be accounted for? A possible explanation may be found in the way suspect communities interpret what they perceive to be just treatment. The group-value model submits that when minority group members experience what they perceived to be fair policing procedures, they interpret this as a message of inclusion, leading to high identification with the group represented by the authority⁶⁴. In this regard, Bradford⁶⁵ found that among UK residents with a non-UK citizenship, procedural justice was strongly linked to social identity as a predictor of cooperation. It is possible that for Muslim passengers, the sense of being included in the majority group represented by airport security officers was important enough to tilt the scale in their favour. While additional studies are required to examine *how* procedural justice and legitimacy can alternate the cooperation of suspect communities, the current finding suggest that the low willingness of suspect community members to cooperate with law enforcement agencies is not a natural law, and may in fact be amended through changes in treatment.

The fact that perceptions of legitimacy and procedural justice were found to affect suspect communities' cooperation in the airport context is particularly interesting. As

mentioned above, airport security is one of the most extreme environments for suspect communities. While everyday policing procedures may sometimes come across as discriminating, airport screening, designed to target passengers from suspect communities, is discriminating by nature and often results in negative feelings of humiliation⁶⁶. If ethnic minorities' perceptions of just procedures can overcome their predisposition of lower cooperation at the airport context, it may be enough to breach the gap between suspect communities and majority groups in other counterterrorism contexts.

While our group of interest was the suspect community of Israeli Muslims, the findings regarding foreign passengers, who are not Israeli citizens, are notable. Foreign passengers were more willing to cooperate with airport security than Israeli Muslim citizens, and the gap between them and the majority group of Israeli Jews disappeared once personal characteristics, and specifically age, were taken into account. The importance of this finding is twofold: first, it highlights the gap between the minority group of Israeli Muslims and the rest of the passengers; and second, it suggests that the motivation of foreigners, non-citizens to cooperate with airport security is not solely based on group identification. As suggested by Weber⁶⁷, as the policing of non-citizens becomes a common procedure in the globalized world, the predictors of cooperation among foreign passengers should be subject to further, more focused examination.

The current study has several important limitations. First, the suspect community of Israeli Muslims is, in some aspects, different from other minorities in the US or Europe, questioning the applicability of the findings to other contexts and locations. However, considering the extremely complicated nature of Muslims-Jews relationship in Israel, it is reasonable to assume that the effect of ethnicity on cooperation could be equally reduced in other, less diverse societies⁶⁸. Second, as in all observational studies, based on surveys and measuring attitudes rather than behaviour, causal conclusions on actual cooperation cannot be

drawn solely based on the current findings. As the survey was conducted within the airport, briefly after security procedures, some of the passengers may have felt compelled to answer the questions suggesting willingness to cooperate. Therefore, we encourage future studies to further explore passengers' attitudes and behaviour using experimental research designs. However, in view of the objective challenges embedded in counterterrorism research in highsecurity environments such as airports, we believe that despite these limitations the current findings offer substantial contribution to our understanding of passengers' cooperation, suggesting potential pathways to improve the relations with suspect communities and increase mitigation.

Conclusions

The willingness of passengers from the suspect community of Israeli Muslims, and the gap between their attitudes towards cooperation and those of other passengers, were tested in the context of aviation security. The results of an attitude survey conducted among 1970 Israeli Jews, Israeli Muslims and foreign passengers at the Ben-Gurion international airport in Israel indicate that passengers from the majority group of Israeli Jews were most willing to cooperate with airport security, and that Israeli Muslim passengers were the least willing to cooperate. However, when considering passengers' perceptions of airport security Legitimacy and procedural justice, Muslim passengers were more willing to cooperate with airport security than all other passengers. We suggest that the gap between ethnic minorities and others in cooperation can be undermined via the encouragement of just procedures and the construction of trust between police and suspect communities.

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Tables

Table 1: Factor Analysis Differentiating Cooperation, Legitimacy, Procedural Justice, and Effectiveness

Item	1	2	3	4
<i>Willingness to Cooperate</i>				
I will not hesitate to give information to security officers.	0.45			
If asked, I will assist a security officer in any way possible	0.56			
If I have suspicions regarding a person or object at Ben-Gurion airport, I will immediately contact a security officer	0.84			
<i>Legitimacy</i>				
I have trust in the airport security at Ben-Gurion airport		0.43		
I feel appreciation and respect towards the airport security officers		0.53		
Considering the security situation in Israel, the security checks at Ben-Gurion Airport are justified		0.67		
The security division at Ben-Gurion airport makes the right decisions regarding passengers' safety		0.54		
<i>Procedural Justice</i>				
The security officers gave me the feeling that they care about me			0.60	
The security officers treated me with politeness and dignity			0.81	
The security officers treated me with courtesy			0.79	
The security officers at Ben-Gurion Airport treated me fairly			0.60	
Airport security officers at Ben-Gurion airport treated me the same way they treat all other passengers			0.64	
The security checks at Ben-Gurion airport are not sensitive enough to passengers			0.69	

Effectiveness

The security procedures at Ben-Gurion airport contributed to my sense of security on the flight	0.75
The security division at Ben-Gurion airport is efficient in handling security threats	0.74

Eigenvalues	1.55	2.69	2.67	1.53
Explained variance (%)	15.58	19.25	19.13	10.94

Note: N=1970; Extraction method: Alpha factoring. Rotation method: Oblimin with Kaiser Normalization. Only factor loadings >.40 are displayed

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of the Dependent Variable – Willingness to Cooperate

% Agree and Strongly Agree Mean (STD)	Variable			
	All passengers	Israeli Jewish passengers	Israeli Muslim passengers	Foreign passengers
<i>I will not hesitate to give information to security officers.</i>	84.4% 4.33 (.97)	87.1% 4.43 (.91)	79.2% 4.15 (1.05)	87.5% 4.44 (.91)
<i>If asked, I will assist a security officer in any way possible***</i>	85.1% 4.36 (.95)	90.2% 4.54 (.84)	81.3% 4.21 (1.01)	83.9% 4.34 (.96)
<i>If I have suspicions regarding a person or object at BenGurion airport, I will immediately contact a security officer***</i>	87.3% 4.51 (.89)	91.2% 4.61 (.77)	87.7% 4.50 (.90)	81.8% 4.39 (.99)

NOTE: Asterisks denote significance levels from analysis of variance: *** < .001

Table 3: Mean differences of willingness to Cooperate

Passenger's M	Passenger's Mean	Passenger's Mean Difference	SD	95% Confidence interval ethnicity (i) ethnicity (j) (i-j)	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Israeli Jews	4.52	Israeli Muslims	.23***	.03	.14	.32
		Foreign	.13**	.04	.03	.22
passengers						
Israeli Muslims	4.28	Israeli Jews	-.23***	.03	-.32	-.14

		Foreign	-0.10*	.04	-.19	-.01	
passengers							
	Foreign	4.39	Israeli Jews	-.13**	.04	-.22	-.03
passengers							
			Israeli Muslims	.10*	.04	.01	.19

*p_≤.05 **p_≤.01 ***p_≤.001

Table 4: OLS Regression Model Predicting Passengers' Willingness to Cooperate with Airport Security

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
	b	b	b	b	b
	(β)	(β)	(β)	(β)	(β)
<i>Passenger's ethnicity</i>					
Israeli Muslims	-.17 (-.11)***	-.14 (-.10)**	-.10 (-.07)*	.06 (.04)	.08 (.06)*
Foreign	-.10 (-.07)*	-.07 (-.05)	-.10 (-.07)	-.01 (-.00)	.00 (.00)
<i>Socio-demographic characteristics</i>					
Gender (Female=1)		.04 (.03)	.03 (.02)	.00 (.00)	-.00 (-.00)
Marital Status (Single=1)		-.11 (-.07)*	-.07 (-.05)	-.06 (-.04)	-.05 (-.03)
Marital Status (Divorced, separated or widowed=1)		.15 (.05)	.15 (.04)	.06 (.02)	.07 (.02)
Age		.00 (.16)***	.00 (.11)***	.00 (.10)***	.00 (.09)**
Religiosity		.03 (.03)	.00 (.00)	-.00 (-.00)	-.00 (-.00)
Highest degree of education		-.01 (-.02)	.00 (.01)	.01 (.03)	.01 (.03)
Income		.04 (.07)**	.03 (.05)*	.02 (.04)	.02 (.04)
Second survey wave		.08 (.06)*	.08 (.06)*	.06 (.04)	.05 (.04)
<i>Flight-related characteristics</i>					
Travel reason (Not tourism=1)		-.06 (-.04)	-.06 (-.04)	-.05 (-.03)	-.04 (-.03)

Flying alone? (Yes=1)	.01 (.01)	.02 (.01)	.00 (.00)	.00 (.00)
Number of flights in past year	-.00 (-.04)	-.00 (-.02)	.00 (.01)	.00 (.01)
Perceptions of airport security				
Effectiveness		.31 (.40)***	.06 (.08)**	.05 (.06)*
Legitimacy			.45 (.52)***	.38 (.45)***
Procedural justice				.10 (.13)***
R ² (Adjusted R ²)	.01(.01)***	.07(.06)***	.23(.22)***	.37(.36)***
N	1970	1970	1970	1970

Note: *p≤.05 **p≤.01 ***p≤.001
 Multicoliniarity: tolerance≥.380

Appendix 1: Descriptive statistics of control variables

<i>Social Identity</i>	
Passenger's ethnicity	Israeli Jew – 33.4% (reference category) Non Israeli – 31.6% Israeli Muslim – 35% N=1970
<i>Socio-demographic characteristics</i>	
Gender	Male – 55.3% (reference category) Female – 44.7% N = 1943
Age	M=41.44; Range: 18-86; SD=16.20; N=1914

Family status	Married/living with a spouse – 64.1% (reference category) Single – 30.1% Divorced/separated/widowed – 5.8% N=1928
Religiosity	Range: (1)Secular – (4)Very religious Median: (2)Traditional Mode: (1)Secular N=1859
Education	Range: (1)Never went to school – (8)Completed PhD or Equivalent Median, Mode: (6)Completed BA or equivalent N=1936
Income	Range: (1)Much less than average – (5)Much above average Median, Mode: (3)About average N=1885
Wave type	First survey wave– 54.1% (reference category) Second survey wave– 45.9% N=1970

Flight characteristics

Travel reason	Tourism – 67.5% Other – 32.5% (reference category) N=1970
Today I am flying...	Alone – 22.4% Other – 77.6% (reference category) N=1970
Number of flights in the past year (including the present flight)	M=3.38; Range: 0-50; SD=4.78; N=1785

Appendix 2: Descriptive statistics of passengers' perceptions of airport security

Perceptions of airport security

Willingness to cooperate	Range: (1)Strongly disagree – (5)Strongly agree Median – 4.32 Mode: (5) Strongly agree N=1940
Legitimacy	Range: (1)Strongly disagree – (5)Strongly agree Median – 4.21 Mode: (5) Strongly agree N=1962

Procedural justice	Range: (1)Strongly disagree – (5)Strongly agree Median – 4.07 Mode: (5) Strongly agree N=1797
Effectiveness	Range: (1)Strongly disagree – (5)Strongly agree Median – 4.11 Mode: (5) Strongly agree N=1942

Appendix 3: Mean differences of legitimacy perceptions

Passenger's ethnicity (i)	M	Passenger's ethnicity (j)	Mean Difference (i-j)	SD	95% Confidence interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Israeli Jews	4.45	Israeli Muslims	.47***	.04	.38	.56
		Foreign passengers	.21***	.04	.13	.29
Israeli Muslims	3.98	Israeli Jews	-.47***	.04	-.56	-.38
		Foreign passengers	-.26***	.05	-.35	-.15
Foreign passengers	4.24	Israeli Jews	-.21***	.04 .05	-.29	-.13
		Israeli Muslims	.26***		.15	.35

***p≤.001

Appendix 4: Mean differences of procedural justice perceptions

Passenger's ethnicity (i)	M	Passenger's ethnicity (j)	Mean Difference (i-j)	SD	95% Confidence interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Israeli Jews	4.28	Israeli Muslims	.35***	.05	.26	.45
		Foreign passengers	.25***	.04	.15	.34
Israeli Muslims	3.93	Israeli Jews	-.35***	.05	-.45	-.26
		Foreign	-.10*	.05	-.21	-.00

passengers

Foreign

4.03

Israeli Jews

-.25***

.04

-.34

-.15

passengers

Israeli Muslims

.10*

.05

.00

.21

* $p \leq .05$ *** $p \leq .001$